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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
Complex Data Citation	A 'complex' data citation encompasses subsets of elements from multiple collections. See section 3.2 for more information.
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data Augmentation	Data augmentation refers to the process of generating new data by applying various transformations or modifications to the existing data. This is commonly used in machine learning, especially in image, text, and audio data, to artificially increase the size of the dataset.
Data Granularity	The scale or level of detail in a set of data. Data infrastructure can be built around predefined levels of granularity, for which conventions vary. The appropriate level of granularity permits optimization of discovery, access, interoperability, analysis, identification, citation, curation, and more. See the definition in Appendix A .
Data Steward	A newly established role in Research Data Management that ensures the quality and integrity of data throughout the research life cycle. Tasks include responsible data handling, from creation and preparation to use and storage to archiving and sharing or reuse. Guiding principles, policies, and rules supporting data quality and integrity are key to success in this role.
Dynamic Citation	A flexible and adaptable citation is typically used when the source or reference material changes or updates. Unlike a static citation, which remains fixed once published, a dynamic citation may update automatically to reflect changes in the source it references, such as live URLs, changing data, or evolving content.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Principles outlining guidance on research data management best practices addressing Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of research outputs and data.
Kernel Metadata	Kernel metadata is a concise, structured set of terms intended to provide consistent, minimalist descriptions of objects, helping to manage collections in an organised way.
Persistent Identifier (PID)	A persistent identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital resource containing a unique string of characters. An identifier is a label that gives a unique name to an entity: a person, place, or thing.
Reproducibility	See the definition in Appendix A .

Terminology/Acronym		Description
Research Software Contributors		A research software contributor is managing diverse contributions beyond coding done by the software authors, including testing, documentation, debugging, and design/architecture roles in large software projects. One stakeholder may be involved in a specific project component while another has a more general role. Metadata plays a crucial role in keeping track of these contributions.
Research Software Engineer (RSE)		“The term Research Software Engineer (RSE) refers to a professional who combines software development and methodology expertise with deep knowledge of one or more research fields. RSEs focus on developing and/or maintaining research software [...]” ¹
SWHID		SoftWare Hash Identifier. See section 3.1.1.2 .

¹ Netherlands eScience Center. (2023). What is a Research Software Engineer? A definition by the Netherlands eScience Center. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994286>

Executive Summary

This report presents the best practices of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for end users, as defined by seven integrated use case partners participating in the FAIR-IMPACT project. These partners represent diverse scientific domains, including photon and neutron sciences, life sciences, and earth & environmental sciences. Notably, one use case partner withdrew during the task and has not been included in this report.

The use cases span different stages of the research life cycle, demonstrating the critical role of PIDs in processes such as data production workflows, complex data citation events, and the management of metadata and sensitive data. Key topics explored include versioning, granularity, kernel metadata, machine-actionability, and research reproducibility in relation to PID minting practices. Currently, there is a lack of standardised cross-domain guidance and widely accepted best practices on PID usage. This report seeks to address this gap by providing clear, adaptable, and applicable across multiple scientific domains. By developing domain-agnostic recommendations, we aim to broaden the adoption of best practices and maximise the impact of this work. However, achieving cross-domain consensus on PID implementation is inherently complex and requires engagement from the broader research community and input from PID experts. The final recommendations presented in this report result from extensive stakeholder engagement, facilitated through a series of in-person and online workshops organised by task members. These workshops provided a platform for expert discussions, collaborative problem-solving, and validation of the proposed best practices.

FAIR-IMPACT is a three-year project launched in June 2022 under the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) call of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). With the ambitious goal of advancing an EOSC of FAIR data and services, FAIR-IMPACT is committed to implementing FAIR-enabling practices, tools, and services at European, national, and institutional level, fostering a more interoperable and accessible research ecosystem.

1 Introduction

In the evolving landscape of research data management, implementing PIDs has emerged as a critical step adhering to best practice guidelines for end users. This guidance highlights the importance of PIDs in ensuring the accessibility, discoverability, and long-term usability of research outputs and data. As the demand for transparency and reproducibility in research grows, PIDs serve as essential tools that enhance the organisation, traceability, and citation of data, aligning with the FAIR principles — Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. Researchers can significantly improve their data management by adopting PIDs, fostering collaboration and innovation within the scientific community while ensuring that valuable research is preserved and remains easily retrievable for future use.

This report addresses users' needs regarding PID practices in different scientific communities, as identified during the project through engagement with various domain experts and internal development work by use case partners. It aims to guide end users of PID technologies and support adopting robust PID implementation and minting practices for different datasets, workflows, and research objects. These efforts should lead to more precise data citations and broader, more targeted use of PIDs. The initial aim of the task was to explore PID practices from the following viewpoints: PIDs in data production workflows, PIDs in complex data citation, and PIDs for sensitive data. However, an additional focus area emerged during the project: PIDs and metadata management. This is a crucial additional area of investigation, which the LifeWatch use case has examined as part of its metadata catalogue development.

In addition to these four focus areas, the integrated use case partners have documented PID practices related to one or more of the following cross-cutting themes:

1. Scientific reproducibility and machine-actionability
2. Research object type definitions for persistent identification, such as instruments, devices, software, and services
3. Granularity, identifier syntax, and relationships

These aspects are illustrated in [Appendix A](#), along with definitions of the key terms.

1.1 Overview of the use cases

Seven partners represent the use cases on PID implementations in the FAIR-IMPACT project:

- UKRI-STFC — Photon & Neutron sciences
- INRIA — Domain-agnostic (software archiving)
- UNIMAN — Life sciences
- LifeWatch ERIC — Earth and Environmental Sciences
- EMBL-EBI — Life sciences
- INRAE — Computational sciences

- UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA — Social sciences

All use case partners are described and further introduced in [Chapter 3](#).

1.2 Methodology

All use case partners initially drafted a detailed plan describing their intended focus and scope of exploration, which provided a comprehensive overview of the topics to be covered in this task. The use case documentation evolved during the project and was influenced by community engagement and peer support in project meetings. In addition to community engagement, relevant EOSC documentation introduced additional areas of exploration, such as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)², which is explained in more detail in [Appendix B](#).

1.3 End user definition

This report supports research communities by integrating PID practices into FAIR data management. The target group is end users, which, depending on the context, may include different stakeholder groups. Researchers and data stewards are the **primary** target groups of this report.

However, additional target groups may be relevant depending on the domain. The recommendations in chapter 4 outline the most targeted groups, but others might apply. When defining practices for PID usage in relation to instruments, the suggestions are more applicable to research infrastructure scientists and data managers. Researchers are addressed as depositors and reusers of research data and other digital objects in the context of sensitive data. However, the entire lifecycle is considered, including curation and preservation by repositories (e.g., data curators) and updating and changing digital objects in ways that impact their versions, change history and logs, and potentially generate new PIDs.

When defining and identifying practices related to research software, we can further distinguish the roles of end users between research software contributors and research software engineers (RSE). PIDs are beneficial for both source code contributors and software users. These two roles are described in more detail in the Terminology table. The research community is identified as the target group responsible for implementing recommendations related to practices that may vary across different scientific domains. A final important consideration is the growing need to recognise the extra time required for data curation to ensure quality for metadata management, which requires additional funding. This is where research funders play a crucial role.

² https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

1.4 How to read the report

[Chapter 2](#) defines PIDs and the benefits of PID usage and implementation, which are divided into five categories: efficiency, precision, automation, federation, and aggregation. [Chapter 3](#) provides an overview of the use case categories explored and descriptions of each of the seven use cases in this work. The tables in [Chapter 4](#) present recommendations to guide end users in their PID practices. The recommendations are the main part of this report. The appendices include an overview of the EOSC landscape ([Appendix B](#)), policies and strategic documents on PID, and summaries of various community outreach efforts ([Appendix C](#)), which contributed to the input and validation of the recommendation in Chapter 4.

2 Persistent Identifiers

2.1 What is a PID

A PID is a unique and long-lasting reference to an entity, such as a dataset, paper, or person. It is a machine-readable string of characters that conforms to a defined scheme and must be associated with one specific entity (McMurry et al., 2017). The publication and dissemination of science continue to grow rapidly, and science has become increasingly interconnected and global. A wide range of PIDs is available to identify various entities (individuals, organisations, and objects) within the research landscape (Ferguson et al., 2019). This ensures that each entity (individuals, organisations, and objects) has a unique and unambiguous identifier, which enables the automated retrieval of the entity and its associated metadata. In this context, PIDs can be considered the building blocks of research information (Meadows et al., 2019). PIDs play a central role in the Open Science framework. PIDs uniquely identify entities within the research ecosystem, facilitate integration and interoperability, and contribute to the FAIRification of research processes. In other words, their use ensures that research processes align with the FAIR principles of data and metadata.

In this context, PIDs are key to realising an EOSC web of FAIR data and services. Moreover, PIDs hold strategic importance for EOSC, ensuring that data and services are securely linked and accessible and can be used effectively and efficiently.³

2.2 Why PIDs - Benefits and functionalities

Assigning and using PIDs provides excellent benefits to the broader research community. The RDA Working Group on National PID Policies completed an extensive survey and literature review on workflows and use cases related to various PID usages. Hugo, W. et al.⁴ later

³ Mejias, G., Cousijn, H., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., van Lieshout, N., Tatum, C., & Lambert, S. (2023). M3.1 - Joint value proposition by relevant PID providers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798215>

⁴ Hugo, W., Van de Sompel, H., & Hakala, J. (2024). The PID Landscape - a Technical View (0.8.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11108203>

divided that study into five main categories regarding the benefits of PID usage and implementation: efficiency, precision, automation, federation, and aggregation.

1. **Efficiency:** The most commonly identified benefit is reducing the administrative, collation, and verification burden placed on researchers, funders, research managers, infrastructure providers, and research-performing organisations across many workflows. Resolvable links and robust metadata facilitate increased interoperability.
2. **Precision:** PIDs enable more precise citation and attribution; more accurate metadata on co-authors, affiliations, and funding; better tracking of data sources for scientific results with appropriate granularity; improved reporting and assessment; and increased data interoperability. They facilitate the allocation of proper credit through citation and enhance trust through transparent metadata and provenance while supporting reproducibility.
3. **Automation:** As scientific service and administrative workflows become increasingly automated, identifiers are essential to enable the execution of this automation with minimal errors. Improving machine actionability through PIDs is a direct objective of the FAIR principles.
4. **Federation:** PIDs simplify the federation and/or integration of various service types, including linked open-data-based contextualisation of resources.
5. **Aggregation:** At all scales, aggregating information about entities and their relationships supports strategic analysis, benchmarking, monitoring, and evaluation. The emergence of PID Graphs and scientific knowledge graphs will increasingly depend on precise referencing via PIDs.

2.3 Different types of PIDs for different purposes

In addition to considering PID minting and implementation practices, the identifiable research object type affects the type of PID to mint. Assigning PIDs for different kinds of research objects, whether digital or digital representations of physical ones, is helpful because they act as pointers to an object and enable connections between various research objects, including contributors and affiliations. This promotes the findability, accessibility, and reproducibility of research outputs. Below, you will find explanations of some of the different PID types and the contexts in which these are typically used. Table 1 does not provide an exhaustive list of PID types, nor an exhaustive description of objectives.

Type of PID - For what purpose?	PID objective
Research outputs	An identifier is assigned to a significant outcome of the research process, such as research articles, data, reports, and other outputs. Digital object identifiers (DOIs ⁵) are the most commonly used PID for research outputs, whether physical, digital, or abstract. The referenced object/entity can also be considered a citable subset rather than an output, for example, in cases where a new dataset or object is created as a source through a query.
People	An identifier is assigned to a person to distinguish them from others. ORCID iDs ⁶ are the most commonly used PID for individuals participating in research, scholarship, and innovation. Researchers, scientists, and authors use ORCID iDs to identify themselves uniquely and to create an online CV that can be integrated into various research workflows and systems.
Organisations	An identifier assigned to organisations in the research landscape covers funders, universities, research institutions, government agencies, and publishers. Research Organization Registry (ROR) ⁷ IDs are commonly used PIDs for organisations in the research sector that include descriptive information about that organisation.
Samples	An identifier is assigned to physical or material samples or a feature of interest (the real-world feature from which the sample is taken). They are not used for digital representations of the sample. The International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) ⁸ ID and the RRID ⁹ are examples of PIDs specifically used for samples. IGSN IDs are a type of DOI assigned by DataCite ¹⁰ to enable connections between research activities and the physical objects associated with them.
Instruments	An identifier is assigned to instruments, including calibration data. As calibration data are considered working data, they should be

⁵ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁶ <https://orcid.org/>

⁷ <https://ror.org/>

⁸ <https://ev.igsn.org/>

⁹ <https://rrid.site/>

¹⁰ <https://datacite.org/>

	appropriately stored and identified by a handle. ¹¹¹² The metadata schema to be used for instruments is PIDINST (PID for INSTRuments). ¹³
Research software	An identifier is assigned to software, with the identifier type depending on the situation at hand, whether citing a software version, crediting its authors, or referencing content-based items, such as linking to a source code excerpt, a commit, etc. For citation and authorship, a DOI is typically used, whereas for content-based references, a Software Hash Identifier (SWHID) serves as an intrinsic identifier.

Table 1: Different types of PIDs for different purposes

3 Introduction to PID use cases - Background and ambition

3.1 PIDs in data production workflows

A data production workflow is a structured sequence of processes and tasks that generate, capture, and manage data throughout its lifecycle. It typically spans from the initial data creation or collection to its final use, storage, and sharing.

Key considerations:

- Automation: Where possible, automate steps such as data validation, cleaning, and processing to improve efficiency and reduce human error.
- Version Control: Maintain proper versioning for kernel metadata and the object or concept referenced by the PID to track changes over time and ensure reproducibility.
- Collaboration: In multidisciplinary environments, ensure that all collaborators can effectively contribute to the workflow using standardised tools and communication channels.
- Data Preservation: Document the provenance of technical data, as this is essential for long-term preservation due to, for example, changing file formats over time.

¹¹ Description of handle: <https://www.pidconsortium.net/?faq=what-are-pids-and-what-are-handles>

¹² McCafferty_Persistent_Identifiers_Instruments, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.48813/hnjw-4v61>

¹³ <https://docs.pidinst.org/en/1.0a1/white-paper/metadata-schema.html>

In this context, we examine how PIDs can best be leveraged during a research lifecycle. Each stage should be carefully defined to ensure the integrity, reusability, and reproducibility of the final dataset and the other research outputs.

3.1.1 Use cases - Descriptions and recommendations

3.1.1.1 UKRI-STFC

This use case explores and advances the use of PIDs for instruments in the context of Photon and Neutron (PaN) large-scale scientific facilities (research infrastructures). PIDs for instruments are an area of growing interest in the community. Two previous European projects, ExPaNDS¹⁴ and PaNoSC¹⁵, produced many high-quality results for the PaN community relating to FAIR data. However, pursuing certain aspects in detail was not possible, including PIDs for instruments. As such, the FAIR-IMPACT project offered an opportunity to further advance FAIR in the PaN community. **Whilst the work has focused on this community, the findings and recommendations may also be relevant to other domains.**

During the project, STFC engaged with two facilities:

- The first was the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source,¹⁶ a world-leading centre for research at the STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. There, the neutron and muon instruments provide unique insights into the properties of materials on the atomic scale.
- The second was the Diamond Light Source (DLS),¹⁷ the UK's national synchrotron science facility.

The use case draws on the Research Data Alliance Working Group outputs on Persistent Identification of Instruments,¹⁸ which takes a cross-domain approach. It focuses on the practicalities of implementation using the PIDINST schema, building on the prototype application implemented at Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie (HZB)¹⁹. Working with two facilities helps identify commonalities and differences in approaches or potential implementations. The facilities already engage in collaborative efforts and shared resources. For example, the ICAT project²⁰ is an open-source metadata management system for large-scale facilities (collaborators include ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, DLS, and HBZ).

¹⁴ <https://www.expands.eu>

¹⁵ <https://www.panosoc.eu>

¹⁶ <https://www.isis.stfc.ac.uk/>

¹⁷ <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/>

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg>

¹⁹ [Persistent Identifiers for Instruments at HZB](#)

²⁰ [The ICAT Collaboration | ICAT Project](#)

The use case originally planned to work with the Central Laser Facility to define the recommended PID practices for instruments, but time constraints made this impractical.

The work focused on drafting potential workflows, mapping metadata requirements, and identifying roles and responsibilities while involving facility scientists and research support roles. The approach examined how infrastructures and workflows might be adapted to accommodate the new requirements for assigning PIDs to instruments. Simulating the theoretical assignment of PIDs using the PIDINST schema highlighted where decisions need to be made and whether exceptions need to be addressed.

The PIDINST schema does not specify a particular PID type or service provider. Since STFC already uses the services of DataCite, the working assumption for this use case is based on using DataCite as a service provider and DOIs as the identifier type, leveraging existing services and reducing requirements for new services. However, this may require review if the theoretical investigations progress to an implementation phase. The PIDINST working group²¹ conducted mappings of the PIDINST schema against DataCite metadata schema²², and we did not repeat the work or test the implementation.

The initial fundamental points of exploration for the use case included providing definitions of an instrument and identifying what the PID should be assigned to. Two related aspects—**granularity and versioning—were also considered.**

Granularity: The RDA work emphasises that there is no definitive answer on what to assign a PID to and that it depends on the needs and working environment of the institution. Drawing on the experiences of HBZ, the work considered an instrument as being a beamline rather than the individual detectors or components within it; this approach is reflected in how instruments are named. For example, in this context, Engin-X²³ is an instrument at ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, as a PID would be assigned to Engin-X to identify the whole instrument. Starting at the “top” level of the instrument does not preclude looking at more granular descriptions in the future. Defining instruments at a high level with clear comparisons to current practices helps explain and work through the requirements engaging different stakeholders.

Versioning (see [Appendix A](#) for a brief definition): Versioning discussions identified three scenarios for PID assignment:

- current/existing instruments
- new instruments
- changes to instruments and versioning (e.g., upgrades)

²¹ <https://docs.pidinst.org/en/latest/index.htm>

²² [schema/schema-datacite.rst at master · rdawg-pidinst/schema · GitHub](https://github.com/rdawg-pidinst/schema/blob/master/schema-datacite.rst)

²³ <https://www.isis.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/engin-x.aspx>

A situation may arise where a PID must be assigned to an “old” instrument; this scenario has not yet been examined but would draw on the same approaches. All scenarios have commonalities, but there are more complex decisions to be made about what changes to an instrument would trigger the requirement for a new PID to be assigned and whether it is a version of the same instrument or if the changes are significant enough to be considered a “new” instrument. For example, **if an instrument upgrade results in a new name, this would indicate the need for a new PID.** However, some cases may be less clear-cut. Again, **the guidance from the RDA work clarifies that this is an institutional decision. Any decision on versioning must be documented, justifiable, and practical to implement with transparent governance to ensure consistency.**

The **InstrumentType** relates to **granularity and versioning**. **InstrumentType is a recommended property in the original PIDINST metadata schema²⁴. Accurately defining instruments is essential,** particularly where PIDs distinguish multiple types of instruments in a research infrastructure or identify parts/components of an instrument. One challenge is defining the instrument meaningfully without a controlled vocabulary or ontology. Decisions on this are still to be clarified in our use case and through the various formal and informal collaborations within the PaN community, there are ample opportunities to reach a common understanding. Practically, if the instrument web page is used as the landing page (as outlined below), it can provide a detailed description of the referenced object.

Regardless of the working environment, a clear and shared understanding of assigning PIDs is necessary, especially with regards to:

- what constitutes a significant change
- the practical implications of the decisions

STFC recommends that institutions develop internal policy guidance outlining the agreed-upon approaches, decision-making process, and responsibilities on the usage of PIDs.

The PIDINST metadata schema includes limited mandatory properties, such as the landing page. Initial concerns about the additional work needed to generate and maintain landing pages were raised within this use case. Two possible solutions (which are not mutually exclusive) have been considered. One solution is to provide **minimal metadata landing pages**, which could theoretically be generated directly from an ICAT record, however lacking sufficient diversity. An alternative solution is to **modify the existing web pages for the instruments**, providing a more diverse landing page. The second approach is technically straightforward but requires consultation and engagement with multiple teams and stakeholders, as responsibility does not fall solely on one team.

²⁴ [Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments](#)

Broader Recommendations across institution types: Beyond the technical requirements of the PIDINST metadata schema, broader recommendations apply:

- **Establish a clear use case for PID application**
- **Engage stakeholders and identify decision-makers**
- **Define clear responsibilities for different roles**, as implementation may involve multiple teams.
- **Identify existing infrastructure** that can be reused to lower barriers to adoption.

Work on this use case is ongoing, and there is continued engagement within the facilities to validate initial investigations and outstanding technical decisions.

3.1.1.2 INRIA

Software Heritage²⁵ is an international nonprofit shared infrastructure supported by Unesco and INRIA. Its core mission is to collect, preserve, and share publicly available source code. The development history and source code are permanently archived in a uniform data model.

Software Heritage ensures the availability and traceability of software by attributing persistent and intrinsic identifiers called SWHIDs (“SoftWare Hash Identifiers”) to software source code artifacts. Over 30 billion software artifacts in the Software Heritage archive are identified using SWHIDs. **The use of SWHIDs addresses the challenge of dealing with the variable granularity of software artifacts:** source code files, source trees, commits, and other objects typically found in version control systems. **A SWHID is a PID independent of the development platform or technology**, which can be computed from the designated object itself without needing a register to maintain the correspondence. This initiative aims to advance the use of SWHIDs for referencing software source code artifacts.

Software identification involves different practices, depending on whether your focus is describing or referencing software. ‘Describing’ refers to an activity where, e.g., credits are attributed to software authors by citing the project as a whole. ‘Referencing’ refers to an activity where reproducibility checks are performed by accessing the content (i.e., the source code). **PIDs that reference data sets, such as DOIs, help reference software as a project** (i.e., software as a concept, not a digital object). However, **referencing specific software artifacts (i.e., digital objects) with different levels of granularity requires distinct specific identifiers. Identifiers provided by Software Heritage thus permit referencing a particular version of a project’s source code at various levels of granularity:** a snapshot, a release, a directory, or even a single file.

SWHIDs are unique identifiers²⁶ intrinsically linked to software components. The difference between extrinsic and intrinsic identifiers lies in how the relation between the identifier and

²⁵ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/mission/>

²⁶ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/mission/approach>

the designated object is created and maintained. Unlike extrinsic identifiers, SWHIDs do not rely on an external registry. Thus, **end users can recompute identifiers on retrieved objects and verify the match**. This is a complex technical landscape: it may be difficult for end users to get a complete overview of the ecosystem. Software is frequently treated as supplementary material despite being integral to the research publication.

A working group²⁷ of experts from different institutions was launched in March 2023.²⁸ An agreement on a standard was reached in June 2023, leading to the publication of the first stable version of the SWHID specification,²⁹ which describes how SWHIDs are computed. The relevance of SWHIDs goes far beyond source code and Software Heritage. The attribution of SWHIDs necessitates built-in deduplication, and the database of the archive itself must implement a dedicated data model. Thus, software artifacts found externally are added to Software Heritage only if a corresponding node with a matching intrinsic identifier does not already exist in the graph—file content, commits, entire directories, or project snapshots are all deduplicated, incurring storage costs only once.

The related challenges vary depending on the stakeholder. The **end-user-oriented challenges lie in understanding why software calls for a specific PID, as software and data have distinct concerns, and in understanding the type of PID compatible with a particular need**.

- **Recommendations for institutions** to facilitate increased adoption of software identification practices by end users:
 - **Develop documentation and support actions** to promote the use of SWHIDs.
 - **Continue expanding the learning materials** already developed by Software Heritage.
 - **Strengthen partnerships with service providers** to develop reliable tools and disseminate them across communities.
 - **Implement toolkits using a “train-the-trainer” approach** to facilitate scalability.
 - **Encourage adoption by involving data/software stewards and research software engineers** in various communities.

3.1.1.3 UNIMAN

This use case³⁰ is centred around the University of Manchester’s involvement in the WorkflowHub,³¹ a registry of computational FAIR workflows. WorkflowHub is sponsored by the European Research Infrastructure ELIXIR and multiple EOSC projects (BY-COVID, BioDT,

²⁷ <https://www.swhid.org/governance/>

²⁸ <https://hal.science/hal-04121507>

²⁹ <https://www.swhid.org/specification/v1.0/>

³⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases/encouraging-and-supporting-researchers-producing-fair-computational-workflows-use-case>

³¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

and EuroScienceGateway) and is now used by over 140 research groups and projects across disciplines. It can reference many workflows, which may be created/stored for use in different workflow systems (e.g., Galaxy, CWL, Nextflow, etc.).

Workflows can be considered scholarly products, encompassing various research outputs (PFDs, text files, images, audio, etc.). Hence, there is a need to encourage and support the creation of FAIR Computational Workflows.³² Metadata provided with workflows in WorkflowHub is expressed as an RO-Crate³³ using JSON-LD and schema.org³⁴ vocabulary for Dataset, together with a Bioschemas³⁵ profile for computational workflows. Further PID considerations concerning workflows as FAIR Digital Objects are being developed with EuroScienceGateway³⁶. **The WorkflowHub Signposting approach to PIDs³⁷ is now recognised³⁸ as an example of “Webby FDOs”³⁹, highlighted at FDO2024.⁴⁰**

Since workflows can be complex objects containing various research outputs, these must be formally and persistently identified to enable their reuse by other researchers.

To support the consistent and reproducible use of workflows, we developed the Workflow RO-Crate,⁴¹ a profile of RO-Crate, for describing the workflow and its metadata based on the Bioschemas Computational Workflow profile⁴² [Bacall 2022] with additional definitions such as constants for known workflow systems and licences.

WorkflowHub supports workflow systems such as NextFlow⁴³ and Galaxy,⁴⁴ which develop workflows using GitHub. This method imports workflows from GitHub repositories,⁴⁵ which

³² <https://workflows.community/groups/fair/>

³³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

³⁴ <https://schema.org/>

³⁵ <https://bioschemas.org/>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13225792>

³⁷ <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/48574fab-924b-4879-9c88-914552b1214f>

³⁸ <https://signposting.org/adopters/#workflowhub>

³⁹ Webby FDO: “an approach leveraging web-based components involving Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) and FAIR Signposting to enable packaging of an observing process’ contextual information (e.g., metadata of sensors, geolocation, and links to content stream), together with operational semantics giving machines the information needed to autonomously process (e.g., detect regions of interest in images, Younis et al. 2020) the actual data (Soiland-Reyes et al. 2024)”: <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.8.134757>

⁴⁰ <https://fairdo.org/fdo2024-conference/>

⁴¹ <https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0>

⁴² <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/ComputationalWorkflow/1.0-RELEASE>

⁴³ <https://github.com/nf-core/>

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/iwc-workflows>

⁴⁵ https://about.workflowhub.eu/docs/registering_workflows/adding-files/#git

means **metadata can be maintained upstream by workflow authors and the community and updated along with workflow changes.**

Workflow testing is essential for users and has been further developed in WorkflowHub. The LifeMonitor⁴⁶ service will test the workflow status that complies with **the Workflow Testing RO-Crate⁴⁷ profile, allowing identification of any workflow instability and usability.** Further work is ongoing for Workflow Run RO-Crate⁴⁸, a provenance output format implemented by 7+ workflow engines compatible with WorkflowHub.

Efforts have been made to engage publishers to improve best practices around citation workflows. GigaScience Press⁴⁹ has recently encouraged using WorkflowHub as part of its policies⁵⁰ [Edmunds 2024]. GigaScience highlights the publication⁵¹ by the Netherlands X-omics Initiative, which utilised RO-Crate and WorkflowHub to fully describe their Nextflow workflow⁵² as an FAIR Digital Object. Furthermore, to further publisher awareness/engagement, the Workflow Publisher Forum had an inaugural meeting with representatives from several major publishers in the life sciences, including representatives from Elsevier, GigaScience, PLoS, and Taylor & Francis.⁵³ There is no engagement on the publishers' side with the Workflows Community Initiative,⁵⁴ arising from previous Workflows Community Summits.⁵⁵ **The Workflows Community Initiative is a community of researchers where the FAIR Computational Workflow principles⁵⁶ is formalised based on best practices in several Workflow Management Systems (WfMS) and the FAIR Research Software guidelines.**

⁴⁶ <https://lifemonitor.eu/>

⁴⁷ https://lifemonitor.eu/workflow_testing_ro_crate

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0309210>

⁴⁹ <https://academic.oup.com/gigascience>

⁵⁰ https://academic.oup.com/gigascience/pages/technical_note; <http://gigasciencejournal.com/blog/fair-workflows/>

⁵¹ Anna Niehues, Casper de Visser, Fiona A Hagenbeek, Purva Kulkarni, René Pool, Naama Karu, Alida S D Kindt, Gurnoor Singh, Robert R J M Vermeiren, Dorret I Boomsma, Jenny van Dongen, Peter A C 't Hoen, Alain J van Gool, A multi-omics data analysis workflow packaged as a FAIR Digital Object, *GigaScience*, Volume 13, 2024, giad115, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giad115>

⁵² De Visser, C., & Niehues, A. (2023). X-omics ACTIONdemonstrator analysis workflow. WorkflowHub. <https://doi.org/10.48546/WORKFLOWHUB.WORKFLOW.402.8>

⁵³ <https://galaxyproject.org/news/2024-08-03-workflow-publisher-forum/>

⁵⁴ <https://workflows.community/>

⁵⁵ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.00019>

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.03490>

3.2 PIDs in complex data citation

The definition of complex data citation generates questions about what defines complexity in data citation. However, it is worth remembering that this work focuses primarily on PID-facilitated complex data citation.

The term '*complex citation*' is applicable when a research study aims to directly cite many digital objects (e.g., datasets, software, physical samples) to reference their sources and maintain the provenance needed for transparency, traceability, and attribution. This approach ensures recognition of these digital assets' continued and growing value while crediting their creators and contributors and enabling the reproducibility of their results. However, implementing a strategy that provides machine-actionable provenance information and validation on all the citations is not straightforward, particularly in cases where:

- Data is aggregated from various resources and stored across multiple repositories, where users must refer back to the sources.
- It is necessary to deal with large, composed datasets, where hundreds or thousands of contributors — responsible for physical samples, instruments, models, code, configurations, quality checks, and curation — must be acknowledged for their specific contributions while excluding unrelated elements.
- Diverse data is organised into collections, and subsets can be accessed and combined to create new dynamic data.
- Data compilations from the literature have metadata for source digital objects stored separately in supplementary databases.
- A research paper cites various digital objects, such as datasets, software, samples, models, figures, audio, and videos, each with unique attributes and requirements.
- Figures and visualisations combine subsets of data from multiple repositories.
- Physical samples are cited, and each paper may utilise specific combinations of these samples.⁵⁷

Several practices aim to address the challenges of large-scale citation in specific use cases, including:

- Creating collections of citations.
- Implementing dynamic data citation generates custom citations for the results of each query on datasets.
- Writing data papers for each subset of data, including detailed provenance and attribution information.
- Providing structured supplementary materials for publications containing links to all referenced resources.

⁵⁷ Agarwal, D., Ayliffe, J., J. H. Buck, J., Damerow, J., Parton, G., Stall, S., Stockhouse, M., & Wyborn, L. (2024). Complex Citation Working Group Recommendation (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106603>

- Packaging (meta)data to capture the provenance of research objects, such as using the RO-Crate structure.
- Publishing subsets of data or a combination of samples as individual objects on platforms like Zenodo ensures that each subgroup is appropriately identified and citable.
- Employing "Reliquary," a concept introduced by the RDA Complex Citation Working Group, involves creating a Complex Citation Object. This is a list of PIDs and metadata essential for identifying digital objects that support the research output while ensuring appropriate credit is given to individual objects and contributors.⁵⁸

While these approaches have challenges, they lay the groundwork for improving complex citation practices and enabling usage evaluation. It also adds value to digital assets used in research studies.

3.2.1 Use cases - Descriptions and recommendations

3.2.1.2 EMBL-EBI

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), is a primary service provider for researchers in the life sciences domain. It provides multiple major research data repositories, such as the Universal Protein Resource (UniProt) and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). EBI is also part of the ELIXIR network that aims to coordinate life sciences resources into a coherent infrastructure.

Complex data citation within EBI is a significant concern, as life sciences publications typically involve multiple independent data deposits into different repositories. This results in constantly adding new data entries to different databases. Moreover, each database includes various data types and schemas and different methods of accessing and visualising entries, further complicating the problem.

Owing to the environment's heterogeneity, **each repository is responsible for linking to related entries in the same or other databases** (typically referred to as **cross-references**). Each entry can contain multiple cross-references, which are generally available on the repository's landing page for that entry.

⁵⁸ Nordling, J., Juty, N., Goble, C., Soiland-Reyes, S., Granger, S., Ramezani, P., L'Hours, H., Neto, R. J., Sennesal, F.-X., Mancarella, F., Matthews, B., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., & Newbold, E. (2023). M3.4 Defining PID Practices in FAIR data management. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10210001>
 PID best practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts and related services (May 2023, online): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VRDcsQg6QdE&t=4071s>
 Why a complex Data Citation WG, Deb Agarwal (May 2023, online): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gLlxdK63-m0&t=906s>

Additionally, **EBI contains resources to facilitate the identification of related entries via cross-references.** One example, OmicsDI,⁵⁹ locates related entries through standard publication cross-references. Another EBI Search collects data from different resources and features text search and cross-reference collection.

In an inter-institution context, the BioProject initiative⁶⁰ aims to describe large-scale research efforts, ranging from genome and transcriptome sequencing efforts to epigenomic analyses to genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and variation analyses. In practice, **a unique identifier aggregates references to research outputs in the same research effort.** This is primarily supported by institutions of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC). The emerging Research Activity Identifier (RAID) is another example of an umbrella identifier with a more generic approach not limited to life sciences.

Recommendations to researchers for referencing complex data in life sciences broadly vary depending on the data type being deposited. EBI recommends using the EBI Submission Wizard⁶¹ and following the ELIXIR guidelines⁶². Generally, it is recommended that depositors use umbrella identifiers such as RAID and BioProject when available to ensure that related entries are correctly added to data deposits when possible. Moreover, when data objects do not already have PIDs, such as DOIs, researchers should reference them using identifiers.org CURIes or URIs, as this provides a global identifier scheme and a CURIE resolution service.

3.2.1.3 INRAE

INRAE is the leading French research organisation specialising in three scientific fields: agriculture, food, and the environment. It proposes new directions through research, innovation, and support for public policies to support the emergence of sustainable agricultural and food systems. This institute comprises 18 research centres spread across French territory, each bringing together multidisciplinary research units.

INRAE also has a department for Open Science called DipSO. This entity is responsible for disseminating good practices for FAIRifying data within the organisation, notably through unique and durable identifiers (PIDs). DipSO also offers software services and technical architectures to support fundamental research and meet open science challenges.

INRAE recommends minting DOIs for documents, research structures, datasets, and software. It also suggests using ORCID to identify people involved in research processes.

⁵⁹ <https://www.omicsdi.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject>

⁶¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/submission/>

⁶² <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines>

Specific resources may have several different types of unique identifiers provided by different systems. For example, software can be identified by SWHID in addition to a DOI.

In addition to producing a recommendation document, DipSO supports researchers with their PID practices by offering software services that help guarantee the durability and uniqueness of identifiers.

INRAE provides an API for the automatic allocation of DOIs. This API can be used by any software system (web application, standalone software, etc.) to associate a unique DOI type identifier with any eligible resource. An institutional triplestore is made available to the INRAE scientific community. This ensures the hosting of thematic thesauri, which serve as repositories of keywords that can be associated with resources using a system of APIs. The triplestore also allows the storage of knowledge graphs. An INRAE research structure can thus decide to represent the resources it manages within a knowledge graph to associate semantic information with raw data. **It is recommended that any data referenced in a graph be assigned a dereferenceable URI in addition to the PID(s) it already has (DOI, for example).** For this, **DipSO offers a service allowing researchers to reserve a root URI (equivalent to an http domain name).** Mostly, this root is chosen specifically for a particular scientific project, **making it possible to produce unique URIs based on this root for all resources produced/used within that project.**

A dereferencing service is also available to ensure the resolution of URIs associated with resources. This service allows you to obtain the description of resources in a format understandable by humans (e.g., a web page) and a format usable by machines (e.g., JSON format).

This technical and software ecosystem can be leveraged for the **citation of complex data.**

At INRAE, as in most scientific institutions, the complexity lies in the fact that there is significant heterogeneity between the types of data managed, and this constitutes an obstacle to cross-referencing information.

Systematising the assignment of unique and persistent identifiers to different data, following the recommendations produced by the institution, is a necessary first step in citation. The tools currently in place provide a response to this need.

We are now studying the use of graphs to express the links between heterogeneous data. Each graph would represent the association of data expressing a particular scientific context; it would itself be uniquely and persistently identified, which would then make it possible to cite this dataset.

3.3 PIDs and sensitive data

When dealing with sensitive data, such as personally identifiable information (PII), health records, or confidential research data, it is crucial to handle PIDs with additional safeguards.

Fine-grained access control mechanisms are required to manage who can create, update, or access PID records, ensuring compliance with privacy regulations such as the GDPR. Proper management ensures sensitive data is protected while enabling its use in research and collaboration, allowing for the seamless integration of PIDs in workflows without compromising data security.

3.3.1 Use cases - Descriptions and recommendations

3.3.1.1 UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA

The UK Data Service is the principal repository for economic, population, and social research data in the UK. It is a partnership between the University of Essex, the University of Manchester, University College London, the University of Edinburgh, and Jisc. The Service is also the UK service provider to the Consortium of Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA). Data within the Service's collection is generally accessible via three access tiers based on the data's detail, confidentiality, and sensitivity. From least to most sensitive, the tiers of access are:

- **Open:** where users are free to access the data without registration.
- **Safeguarded:** where users can access the data once they have registered with the Service and accepted the End User Licence.
- **Secure: (most sensitive):** where the data is subject to the Five Safes framework: safe data, safe projects, safe people, safe settings, and safe outputs.⁶³ As such, users can only access data that has been treated to protect any confidentiality concerns (safe data) through SecureLab (safe settings), our own Trusted Researcher Environment (TRE), once their project has been approved by the data owner (safe projects) and they have passed Safe Researcher Training (safe people). Any outputs are then screened to ensure that they are non-disclosive (safe outputs).

This use case focuses on PIDs assigned to sensitive Social Science data deposited and made available via the UK Data Service,⁶⁴. However, the recommendations may also apply to sensitive data from various disciplines.

In Sensitive Data & Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Repository Lifecycle Factors, the UK Data Service considers the various stages a digital object passes through that may generate relevant changes⁶⁵. For example, the object may be changed during the curation phase, or derived objects may be created. As a result, there may be multiple digital objects derived from a shared source object, i.e., an open, safeguarded, and controlled version. Each item must be

⁶³ Green, E., & Ritchie, F. (2023). The present and future of the Five Safes framework. *Journal of Privacy and Confidentiality*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.29012/jpc.831>

⁶⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases/change-triggers-impacting-pid-generation-sensitive-data-within-social-sciences-0>

⁶⁵ L'Hours, H., Bell, D., & Parkes, O. (2024). Sensitive Data & Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Repository Lifecycle Factors. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12774338>

uniquely identified with its own PID, where the new sensitivity assessment drives routes and conditions for access and reuse.

When a DOI is first minted for an object, a subset of the metadata collected about it is added to the PID metadata. **Sensitive digital objects require additional considerations. The object's sensitivity level will influence what metadata can be shared for discovery and how the digital object can be accessed and reused.**

A new Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is assigned to the study each time there is a significant change to the data, documentation, or metadata. For example, changes could be corrections to the metadata or additional waves in longitudinal studies. The new DOI is an increment of the previous DOI (i.e., <https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-6614-1> would become <https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-6614-2>), and it will resolve to a landing page that contains an entire version history of the data since the allocation of its first DOI. **The DOI system supports resource discovery and simplifies citations for data collection users.** Data producers benefit directly through increased visibility of their work. It also helps to improve the reproducibility of research as, if cited correctly, researchers can see which version of the data was accessed for analysis.

3.3.1.2 EMBL-EBI

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), is a leading service provider for researchers in the Life Sciences domain. It provides multiple major research data repositories, such as the Universal Protein Resource (UniProt) and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). EBI is also part of the ELIXIR network that aims to coordinate life sciences resources into a coherent infrastructure.

This use case focuses on the identifiers.org service. This service provides a global identification scheme for life sciences references via the CURIE standard⁶⁶ and a CURIE resolver that locates the currently available online URLs for given CURIEs. This service acts as a PID provider for life sciences as the CURIEs are globally unique and persistently resolvable via the constant curation of the identifiers.org registry.

Since identifiers.org acts between multiple systems, it must be lightweight enough not to slow down other services. It also has to be easily manageable to keep long-term maintainability viable. As such, one of the core aims of identifiers.org is to maintain the minimum amount of information possible and leave most data management responsibilities to data providers, which aligns with the definition of PID kernel metadata.

This is the basis for implementing PIDs for sensitive data in identifiers.org. **Datasets that contain sensitive data are marked with extra information limited to facilitating the user experience when resolving such PIDs. This information explains why the data is sensitive**

⁶⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2010/NOTE-curie-20101216/>

and how users may request access. The data provider handles all authentication and authorisation and has complete control over the implementation of its service.

3.4 PIDs and metadata management

Metadata management involves organising and maintaining metadata to ensure that research objects are well-described, findable, and reusable across different platforms. Integrating PIDs into metadata management workflows is essential for maintaining long-term integrity and accessibility by providing persistent, machine-actionable links to research resources. In this context, we explore how PIDs can be leveraged to improve governance and citation practices.

3.4.1 Use case - Description and recommendations

3.4.1.1 LifeWatch ERIC

LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium dedicated to advancing e-science in biodiversity and ecosystem studies. It unites diverse scientific communities and connects distributed observatories and research centres into unified, accessible online platforms. To make our resources discoverable and effectively reusable, LifeWatch catalogues resources and provides sufficient metadata, enabling others to understand and leverage their research potential. This use case outlines the use of PIDs to identify resources originally released by different LifeWatch member states.

The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, based on GeoNetwork technology, manages metadata for five types of digital objects: Datasets, Services, Virtual Research Environments, Workflows, and Research Websites. **All submitted resources are assigned a local identifier (a unique string) to facilitate their management within the catalogue. This catalogue supports the creation of DOIs for resources lacking them, pending validation and verification.** Only admin users can accept and manage requests for DOI minting through the GeoNetwork–DataCite connection, **ensuring a controlled and reliable process for location-independent identification.** The DOI resolves to the corresponding web page of the catalogue, where end users can access human-readable and machine-readable metadata about the resource.

Different LifeWatch ERIC nodes may have data repositories for collecting and centralising datasets. For example, the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal is a national data repository that facilitates data sharing for biological and environmental research. This portal implements the Handle System, a global name service that enables secure name resolution and digital object identification independent of location. All datasets submitted to the Data Portal are assigned a Handle, which resolves to the corresponding web page in the Data Portal, where metadata about the datasets and their attributes is available.

The metadata for these datasets must be recorded in the Metadata Catalogue. **Dataset owners should request a DOI in the Metadata Catalogue**, and the generated DOI should be included as an alternative identifier for the dataset in the Data Portal. Additionally, it is recommended to include the Handle obtained from the Data Portal as an alternative identifier for the dataset in the Metadata Catalogue. **Having more than one DOI for a resource is a problem for everyone. When a digital object is not consistently cited, it becomes less likely to be matched correctly. Fragmentation of citation records undermines the effectiveness of PIDs designed to ensure accurate and consistent referencing.** With this strategy of implementing different types of PIDs in the Metadata Catalogue and Data Portal, duplicate DOIs or Handles for the same dataset hosted on these two platforms are avoided. If a dataset already has a DOI or Handle, no new one should be minted to avoid duplication. **The owner should check for existing PIDs and reference them appropriately to maintain consistency.** If a duplication already exists, LifeWatch relies on PID providers to resolve it. A useful resource on this topic can be found in Crossref documentation⁶⁷.

LifeWatch ERIC provides an additional core catalogue for resources derived from Semantic Web technologies. This catalogue, the LifeWatch ERIC Semantic Artefact Catalogue (EcoPortal), stores digital objects such as ontologies, taxonomies, thesauri, and controlled vocabularies. Like the Metadata Catalogue, EcoPortal uses DataCite services to create DOIs upon user request, which are processed through the Administration Console. In addition, DataCite's Fabrica is used as the web interface to manage repository accounts and track and update all DOIs and metadata. The minted DOIs resolve to a summary web page of the hosted artefact in EcoPortal, where the resource and its metadata are accessible.

⁶⁷ <https://community.crossref.org/t/the-problem-with-duplicate-dois-and-how-you-can-help/2634>

4. Best practice recommendations for end users on PID usage & implementation

This section comprises the core content of this report with recommendations organised across nine categories based on their respective topics, guiding end users in their PID practices. The recommendations are derived from use case engagements and align with the key areas of focus explored in those cases. All nine categories of recommendations are presented in a short introductory paragraph, followed by a table. The table helps address the questions ‘what’ - ‘why’ - ‘for whom’ - ‘about’ - ‘from where’. In other words, what is the recommendation, why is this recommendation part of good research practices, for whom is the recommendation for, what is the recommendation about as defined in keywords and lastly, from where has this recommendation been derived.

A PID is applied to a clearly defined digital or a digital representation of an object so that it can be referred to. The recommendations below apply to the infrastructure and practices necessary for using a PID. However, other aspects of PID management must consider the digital objects' lifecycles and how they are changed for research, deposit, curation, preservation, and reuse. Each change to the content defined as part of a digital object (e.g., data, metadata, and associated documentation) **becomes a part of its provenance**. Based on the impact of those changes on the object, its version and PID should be described and detailed with sufficient and appropriate information. This is particularly important as various actors may apply different versions and criteria for when a new PID is needed.

4.1 Identifiers for different Object Types and Purposes

In research, different types of objects require specific identifiers to ensure clarity, provenance, and long-term accessibility. People involved in research processes should be identified using ORCID, a system designed specifically for unambiguous and persistent identification of individuals. For software, SWHID is the preferred identifier, recognising the critical role software plays in data collection, analysis, and dissemination. Unlike data, software is an executable tool with complex architecture and an evolving lifecycle, making traditional data identification methods unsuitable. Additionally, any data referenced in a scientific knowledge graph should have a dereferenceable URI alongside existing PIDs. This allows researchers to create unique, accessible URIs for all resources within a project, ensuring better data management and interoperability.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? 68
A: Identifiers for different Object Types and Purposes				
A1. Use ORCID to identify people involved in research processes, as ORCID is specially designed for identifying people.	To ensure provenance, people need to be persistently and unambiguously identified.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of people 	B ⁶⁹
A2: Use SWHID for identifying software.	<p>“If you don’t have the software, you don’t have the data”⁷⁰: digital data is collected, created, visualised, analysed, interpreted, and disseminated via software. Archiving and referencing (pieces of) software source code is a prerequisite for more robust data workflows. Solutions developed for data are not appropriate for</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Software Contributor • Research Software User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of software artifacts • Referencing • Traceability 	C ⁷²

⁶⁸ All source definitions compiled as a list below the table. All sources are in addition also referenced as footnotes upon first appearance.

⁶⁹ ORCID community: <https://orcid.org/>

⁷⁰ Turello, D. (2019, February 7). How to Think About Data: A Conversation with Christine Borgman [Webpage]. Insights. Scholarly Work at the John W. Kluge Center. [//blogs.loc.gov/kluge/2019/02/how-to-think-about-data-a-conversation-with-christine-borgman/](https://blogs.loc.gov/kluge/2019/02/how-to-think-about-data-a-conversation-with-christine-borgman/)

⁷² INRIA/Software Heritage, SIRS report

	<p>software, as there are significant differences between these outputs (EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020⁷¹):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software is an executable tool • The software relies on a very complex architecture • Software may have a very complex lifecycle: from a “one shot” project to software that will evolve over several decades 			
A3: Assign a dereferenceable URI ⁷³ to any data referenced in a scientific knowledge graph, in addition to existing PIDs.	The dereferenceable URI allows researchers to reserve a root URI. Based on this root URI, researchers can create unique URIs (equivalent to an http domain name) for all resources produced/used within a project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Software Engineer to provide services that support the use of dereferenceable URIs • Researcher to make use of dereferenceable URIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific knowledge graph • Exposure to structured, interlinked, and semantically rich research resources 	D ⁷⁴

Table 2: Identifiers for different Object Types and Purposes

⁷¹ EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat. (2020). Scholarly infrastructures for research software. Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force (TF) SIRS. European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/28598>

⁷³ A dereferenceable URI is an identifier that resolves to a webpage

⁷⁴ INRAE/DipSO (a set of software services)

4.2 Workflows and Scientific Reproducibility Practices

Ensuring scientific reproducibility requires well-documented and accessible computational workflows. Researchers should register their workflows in established repositories, such as the WorkflowHub and Galaxy, recognising them as valuable scholarly outputs that encompass diverse research materials. The Signposting approach enables precise referencing by linking specific parts of an HTML page to PIDs, improving navigation and reproducibility. Additionally, integrating SWHIDs into journals and repositories strengthens research software identification, ensuring the integrity of source code and allowing citation of entire programs or specific components. This integration enhances Software Heritage coverage, improves archival reliability, and enriches the services available to researchers, ultimately supporting more robust scientific reproducibility practices.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? <small>75</small>
B: Workflows and Scientific Reproducibility Practices				
B1: Register computational workflows in established registries and repositories (e.g.,	Registering computational workflows furthers scientific reproducibility. Computational workflows can themselves be considered scholarly products, encompassing various types of research outputs (PDFs, text files, images, audio, etc.).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Owner ● Data Depositor ● Repository and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computational workflows 	E ⁷⁸

⁷⁵ Source definitions below the table

⁷⁸ [WorkflowHub](#) - a registry of computational FAIR workflows

WorkflowHub ⁷⁶ , Galaxy ⁷⁷).		Registry Managers		
B2: Use the Signposting approach ⁷⁹ to allow navigation from an HTML landing page to a specific resource part, where PIDs are leveraged in the redirection.	Allows referencing to a specific part of an HTML page. More precise and targeted references increase the reproducibility of research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computational workflows ● Referencing subsets of resources ● More targeted exact citation 	F ⁸⁰
B3: Integrate SWHIDs into existing workflows within journals and repositories.	Integration of SWHIDs cater for robust and precise identification of research software, which enriches the services offered to the end users and supports scientific reproducible practices. Software identification calls for specific tooling. One should be able to cite the whole or parts of a source code. The integrity of the source code should be ensured: An external identifier may point to an object that may be altered without any notification of the change, whereas an intrinsic identifier reflects such modifications. Such integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Service Provider 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Software deposit ● Intrinsic identifier ● Interconnected and interoperable academic ecosystem ● Referencing software artifacts 	p ⁸¹

⁷⁶ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

⁷⁷ <https://dockstore.org/organizations/iwc>

⁷⁹ Signposting is an approach to make the scholarly web more friendly to machines. More information: <https://researchlibrary.lanl.gov/projects/signposting-the-web/>

⁸⁰ <https://signposting.org/adopters/#workflowhub>

⁸¹ <https://blog.zenodo.org/2024/10/21/2024-10-21-swh/>

	improves Software Heritage coverage by pushing content directly into the archive. Enhancing end users' set of services and scientific reproducibility.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More exact identification 	
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Table 3: Workflows and Scientific Reproducibility Practices

4.3 Versioning Practices

In some cases, any change to the bits comprising an object (as defined through integrity measures such as a checksum) may trigger the creation of a new PID. In other environments, changes considered to be minor (e.g., a spelling correction in metadata or documentation) may only be recorded through the 'change log' metadata within a PID. Defining and communicating the approach to change, versioning, and minting new PIDs for derived digital objects becomes a dependency for applying the more dynamic recommendations below, including granularity, citation, and maintenance.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? 82
C: Versioning Practices				
C1: Develop a versioning policy/procedure of PIDs and	How (which rules and by whom) versioning is handled must be clear to ensure the integrity of the data and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Owner • Data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Versioning policy 	L ⁸³

⁸² Source definitions below the table

⁸³ CESSDA Training Team (2024). CESSDA Data Archiving Guide version 3.0. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC. <https://dag.cessda.eu/Chapter-4/5-Updates-and-versioning>

<p>referenced objects that provides clear guidance on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is allowed to request changes; • Who will record these changes; and • Where these changes are recorded. <p>Recommendations C1-C4 should be considered and applied jointly.</p>	<p>documentation material by maintaining a structured history of changes, enabling traceability, and preventing data loss or corruption.</p>	<p>Depositor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository Manager 		
<p>C2: Communicate the boundaries constituting a minor change or a significant change.</p>	<p>Significant and/or minor changes may lead to other versioning actions, such as generating a new PID.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Owner • Data Depositor • Data Administrator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data augmentation 	<p>L</p>
<p>C3: Check if the repository communicates whether a significant change (and/or a minor change) leads to generating a new PID.</p>	<p>Proper versioning practices help improve the reproducibility of research as, if cited correctly, researchers can see which version of the data was accessed for which analysis. A new PID resolves to a complete version history of the object system, supports resource discovery, and simplifies citations for data collection users. Data producers also benefit directly through the increased visibility of their work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Owner • Data Depositor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Versioning instructions 	<p>N⁸⁴</p>

⁸⁴ UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA use case

<p>C4: Communicate file naming conventions clearly and apply them across all copies and versions in all formats and locations.</p>	<p>It must be clear to all parties what the most recent data version is. A file naming convention is a structured and consistent approach to naming files to improve organisation, traceability, and reproducibility of research data. A well-designed convention helps researchers quickly identify file contents, version history, and relationships between files.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Owner ● Data Depositor ● Data Curator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● File naming convention 	<p>M⁸⁵</p>
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Table 4: Versioning Practices

4.4 Data Granularity Practices

Effective versioning practices ensure that data is structured at the right level of detail, balancing usability, efficiency, and reproducibility. The appropriate data granularity depends on the type of data and its intended re-use, enabling accurate citation, validation, and interoperability. Machine-actionable identifiers further enhance data discoverability by allowing citations at various levels of granularity, from entire datasets to specific subsets. Research communities often establish best practices for granularity, ensuring consistency and credibility across studies. Additionally, PIDs should be assigned to subsets of datasets, workflows, and software components to guarantee provenance and recognition for contributors. Standards like W3C PROV help maintain context and traceability, particularly in complex research environments where datasets are combined and analysed. By adhering to these principles, researchers enhance reproducibility, improve data citation, and facilitate more precise referencing of digital resources, including audiovisual content and software artifacts.

⁸⁵ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/format-your-data/versioning/>

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? 86
D: Data Granularity Practices				
D1: Consider what best serves the needs of potential re-use. The correct data granularity level also depends on the data type at hand.	Proper data granularity practices ensure that data is structured at the appropriate level of detail, balancing usability, efficiency, and reproducibility. This will lead to enhanced data reusability and interoperability, e.g. through more accurate data interpretation and increased computational performance and analysis, but also data validation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Granularity ● Re-usability 	G ⁸⁷
D2: Enable more machine-actionability of the data by using machine-actionable identifiers. This makes citation at various levels of granularity possible, even to the most fine-grained level.	Unlike people, machines can deal with very high levels of granularity and support discovery, accessibility, and interoperability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Granularity ● Machine-actionability 	G

⁸⁶ Source definitions below the table

⁸⁷ PIDs in complex data citation workshop

<p>D3: Allow for citation at several levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The semantic artefact • The versioning of entities inside the artefact • Linking between deprecated and valid entities 	<p>Large datasets associated with satellites (or other instruments) commonly have good data management plans and DOIs that can be referenced. However, the entire dataset is not widely used in any research effort. Navigating different levels of granularity and accurately identifying the specific data used is crucial for ensuring the citation of subsets of the datasets and, thus, reproducibility.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exact data citation • Granularity • Versioning • Semantic artefact 	<p>G</p>
<p>D4: Find out if your research community has defined granularity practices and adhere to them if available. These practices are often determined through consensus or the best practices shared within the community.</p>	<p>Some research areas have agreed-upon guidelines or standards for how detailed or broad data or findings should be presented. For example, in fields like data science or machine learning, researchers may have standards on granular data, e.g., whether to use raw or aggregated data. If such standards or practices have been established, it is essential to follow them to ensure consistency, reliability, and alignment with peers' expectations. Following these practices can improve the credibility of findings and make research comparable with others in the field.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research community • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version granularity 	<p>G</p>

D5: Use handles to refer to a specific part of a lengthy video, as handles can address video fragments.	This procedure allows very exact citations to specific parts of audiovisual resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Citation granularity ● Audiovisual resource 	G
D6: Assign a PID and new metadata to the subsets of a dataset used in an analysis to guarantee the provenance of the resulting data. This metadata needs to contain both context and provenance information.	In the Virtual Research Environment, a dataset can be filtered and composed from multiple other datasets and analysed by services, resulting in a new dataset. Ensuring the provenance of this new dataset is essential for providing recognition to all involved research contributors. Recommended standards, such as the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) PROV, ⁸⁸ are available.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dataset granularity ● Research analysis ● Metadata ● Provenance 	G
D7: Assign a PID to collections and related components. A workflow is a collection that also contains executables.	Data-centric solutions may not adequately address the unique requirements of different software components. It is worth noting that software can be compared to a "data type", and once the source code is converted into binaries, it then turns into an "executable". ⁸⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Workflow granularity ● Software 	G

Table 4: Data Granularity Practices

⁸⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

⁸⁹ An executable file (EXE file) is a computer file that contains an encoded sequence of instructions that the system can execute directly when the user clicks the file icon. <https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/definition/executable-file-exe-file>

4.5 Complex Data Citation Practices

Accurate and consistent citation is crucial for research transparency, particularly when handling complex data. To maintain consistency, only one PID of the same type, such as a DOI, should be assigned to each unique digital object. Assigning multiple PIDs of the same type can lead to fragmentation and errors in citation matching. It’s also essential to properly credit contributors using systems like the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) to ensure clear attribution within research teams. Dynamic citations, such as those using tools like Zotero or OpenCitations, allow for flexibility in citing evolving datasets and resources. By incorporating versioning and linking multiple identifiers to the same object, researchers can track the history of the data and ensure they are referencing the correct version, enhancing accessibility and reproducibility. Additionally, linking research objects when multiple identifiers exist ensures better discoverability and citation consistency, especially when datasets are updated or modified over time.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? <small>90</small>
E: Complex Data Citation Practices				
E1: Only assign one PID of the same type for each unique	If several PIDs of the same type (e.g., DOIs) are assigned per record, they become less likely to be matched correctly. Fragmentation of citation records undermines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data citation 	A ⁹¹

⁹⁰ Source definitions below the table

⁹¹ LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue

digital object to allow consistent citations.	the effectiveness of PIDs, which are designed to ensure accurate and consistent referencing.			
E2: Use Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) ⁹² to cater for proper accreditation within a research group or project.	Proper citation, no matter how complex, ensures research transparency. This makes it easier for researchers to be as accurate as possible in identifying the datasets or partial datasets used in their research. Clearly defining roles at the start of a research project and making adjustments as needed throughout can help streamline the process, reducing confusion and minimising the risk of disputes during the reporting and writing stages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data citation • Contribution roles 	G
E3: Make use of dynamic citations in cases where the source or reference material might change or be updated over time, e.g., by making use of Zotero ⁹³ or OpenCitations. ⁹⁴	Collections are living objects, i.e., they change depending on needs. A dynamic citation is flexible and adaptable, typically used in contexts where the source or reference material might change or be updated over time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic citation 	G
E4: Cite dynamic data dynamically via query: data +	Using the query to identify the dataset provides valuable semantic information on how the dataset was	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic citation 	G

⁹² <https://credit.niso.org/>

⁹³ <https://www.zotero.org/>

⁹⁴ <https://opencitations.net/>

<p>timestamp or TMS (time management system) when it follows a versioned history.</p>	<p>constructed, rather than just having a raw data dump. Additionally, scalable dynamic data citation enables users to re-execute the query with the original timestamp to retrieve the original data while accessing the latest version with all updates and changes. This allows for a comparison of the resulting differences. This approach is supported by the RDA Data Citation WG.⁹⁵</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Query 	
<p>E5: Add a link between the research objects if multiple identifiers point to the same object. Versioning adds a layer of complexity.</p>	<p>Linking multiple identifiers to the same object ensures that researchers can access the object through various citation systems or databases, increasing its visibility and accessibility. Linking identifiers allows for better tracking of the object's history, especially when versioning adds complexity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data citation • Linking objects 	<p>G</p>

Table 5: Complex Data Citation Practices

4.6 PID Ownership and Maintenance

Managing the ownership and responsibility of PIDs is essential for ensuring accurate and reliable data citation. To streamline this process, PID management should be bundled with existing agreements, such as software licenses, to clarify ownership and transfer responsibilities. While automation can simplify PID minting and metadata management, human oversight remains critical to maintaining quality and accuracy. Automated systems can populate and update metadata fields, but regular reviews by a human owner are necessary to ensure precision. Proper budgeting for these human-curation processes is essential when implementing PIDs to ensure long-term data integrity.

⁹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-citation-wg/activity/>

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? 96
F: PID Ownership and Maintenance				
F1: Manage PID responsibility and ownership by bundling these with other existing agreements, such as software licenses.	There is often confusion about PID and PID metadata ownership, responsibility, and transfer. Using already-existing agreement infrastructures like software licences can make this easier to address and track.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher ● Data Curator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID ownership ● Licensing 	H ⁹⁷
F2: Make sure to allow automation of PID minting and metadata management, but human curation remains crucial in ensuring quality and must be budgeted for.	Many metadata fields can be automatically populated and updated when integrating PIDs into research workflows. However, they must be periodically reviewed by a human owner to ensure accuracy, which should be budgeted for when implementing PIDs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Curator ● Researcher ● Research Funder / Research Performing Organisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human data curation ● Data quality assurance 	H

Table 6: PID Ownership and Maintenance

⁹⁶ Source definitions below the table

⁹⁷ “EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices” workshop. [Material](#) and [recording](#).

4.7 Kernel Metadata Practices

Kernel metadata practices are crucial for ensuring that data is well-documented and accessible without compromising security or privacy. To avoid complications with permissions, sensitive information should not be included in kernel metadata. Any additional, sensitive metadata can be stored separately, ensuring proper access controls. Ownership and access decisions should lie with the data owner and provider, not upstream actors, and researchers should consult institutional and national stakeholders for guidance on best practices. As discussions on standardising kernel metadata continue at local and international levels, it is important to define whether data is "open" or "closed" in the kernel metadata to clarify terms of use. Kernel metadata plays a key role in describing physical objects, such as instruments or samples, ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and proper interpretation of data by providing essential context like calibration records and environmental conditions.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? <small>98</small>
G: Kernel Metadata Practices				
G1: Avoid sensitive metadata in the kernel metadata.	Having no sensitive data in the kernel removes the need for authentication and permissions for kernel metadata. Additional layers (separate files) of non-kernel metadata can be deployed if necessary. Furthermore, the decision to grant access does not lie with the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID Manager to enact/enable ● Researcher to make use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sensitive metadata 	¹⁰⁰

⁹⁸ Source definitions below the table

¹⁰⁰ Internal FAIR-IMPACT kernel metadata discussions

	upstream actors (Provider, Authority) but with the Owner and the Provider ⁹⁹ .			
G2: Consult institutional and national stakeholders on recommended kernel metadata practices.	Discussions on attributes to be included in the kernel metadata are ongoing; for now, agreement on kernel metadata takes place at the local/national level. Work is in progress on reaching mutually agreed-upon practices and kernel metadata content at an EOSC/international level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreed kernel metadata practices 	I
G3: Include the notion of “open” or “closed” in the kernel metadata.	Kernel metadata, with its machine-readable metadata, efficiently manages vast amounts of records. Defining whether it is open or closed is crucial for identifying the terms of use and conditions for querying data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID Service Provider to enact/enable ● Researcher to define 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open vs. closed 	I

⁹⁹ For more information on PID Roles, see: van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2024). D3.3 - Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PID Policy (V2.0 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14092489> and EOSC PID Policy: European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R., Manghi, P. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

<p>G4: Include kernel metadata, especially when describing physical objects, e.g., instruments or samples.</p>	<p>For instruments and samples, this metadata ensures that their use, conditions, and modifications can be traced over time, which is critical for reproducibility and verifying results. Furthermore, these types of objects have variable properties depending on their conditions or handling. Including kernel metadata allows researchers to accurately interpret data by providing detailed context, such as calibration records for instruments or environmental conditions for samples. This level of detail ensures that the data is understood and used appropriately.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID Service Provider to enact/enable ● PID User to describe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Describing physical objects 	<p>I</p>
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Table 7: Kernel Metadata Practices

4.8 Sensitive Data Practices

Managing sensitive data requires a comprehensive lifecycle approach, especially when assigning PIDs and updating metadata. It is essential to evaluate the compatibility of predefined terms, licenses, and rights-related information with the repository's terms of deposit, ensuring that rights are properly conveyed to data re-users. Sensitive digital objects must be protected with robust rights management metadata, and any pre-existing PIDs or provenance history should be carefully considered when updating records. Transparency in provenance is critical to maintaining trust. Repositories may alter object structures during curation, which could necessitate updates to metadata or the assignment of new PIDs. Additionally, versioning models must be defined and consistently applied to digital objects to ensure accurate tracking of changes. Any sensitivity assessments should be clearly communicated, along with any access barriers, to ensure researchers understand the conditions for discovering, accessing, and reusing sensitive data.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? 101
H: Sensitive Data Practices				
H1: Take a lifecycle perspective on sensitive metadata issues for PIDs.	Assigning PIDs and updating metadata should consider the digital objects deposited alongside repositories' curation and preservation steps.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance 	J ¹⁰²
H2: Evaluate predefined terms and conditions, licences, or other rights-related information and whether these are compatible with the terms of deposit and rights required by the repository, including rights to be passed on to data re-users.	Rights management metadata recorded with the PID protects sensitive digital objects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance 	J
H3: Consider if one or more PIDs are already assigned to one or more parts of the object and whether the existing PID approach will	If the repository applies its own PIDs, historical digital object records may need to be updated to point to newly minted PIDs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance 	J

¹⁰¹ Source definitions below the table

¹⁰² Sensitive Data & Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Repository Lifecycle Factors. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12774337>

be continued or replaced by one set by the repository.				
<p>H4: Evaluate any pre-existing provenance history of custody and change and consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will the pre-deposit provenance and history be retained and communicated to end users? • If and how will this influence the repository's own approach to recording provenance information? 	Transparency of provenance is critical to trust in sensitive digital objects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance • Provenance 	J
<p>H5: Define a straightforward object model (data, metadata, and associated documentation) for the deposit and whether the existing object model structure will be maintained or revised by the repository during curation, quality, and compliance activities.</p>	Digital objects may be reorganised, restructured, or relabelled to align with repository practice, triggering a need to update change logs or generate a new PID.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance • Object model definition 	J
<p>H6: Evaluate whether a deposit includes an associated version model for defining how the identifiers have been assigned and the terms by which they, or related metadata,</p>	Change and versioning rules for digital objects must be consistently applied and communicated to end users. These rules influence updates to change logs and new PIDs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance • Version 	J

would be changed in response to changes in the object. Decide whether this versioning model will be retained or if the repository's versioning practice will be applied.			model	
H7: Evaluate whether there is a pre-existing assessment of the digital objects' sensitivity and whether the repository will accept the assessment method and outcome provided or apply its approach to sensitivity assessment moving forward. It must then be recorded whether the repository's assessment concludes that some or all digital objects are sensitive.	Any inconsistency in approach or sensitivity assessment between the time of deposit and subsequent access and reuse should be documented, justified, and communicated.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance • Sensitivity assessment 	J
H8: Communicate sensitivity assessments and any barriers (to humans and or machines) to access digital objects.	Clarity on whether a researcher can immediately or potentially access a digital object for some sensitivity-related reason reduces the barriers to discovering, accessing, and reusing digital objects relevant to research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Curator • PID Manager • Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality assurance • Access Restrictions 	K ¹⁰³

Table 8: Sensitive Data Practices

¹⁰³ Sensitive Data: Persistent Identifier (PID) Semantics Gaps. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12774041>

4.9 Instrument Practices

Defining clear guidelines for when changes to an instrument require a new PID is essential for maintaining consistency and clarity in research workflows. A shared understanding of what the PID identifies and how versioning is applied ensures all stakeholders are on the same page. Organisations should develop comprehensive policies for assigning PIDs to instruments, ensuring that the process aligns with both internal practices and external standards. The PIDINST metadata schema provides a domain-agnostic approach, helping organisations implement consistent PID practices that foster the sharing of best practices and encourage collaboration across research domains.

Recommendation - What?	Problem statement - Why?	Stakeholder affected - For whom?	Keywords - About?	Source - From where? <small>104</small>
I: Instrument Practices				
I1: Define and agree when changes to an instrument require a new PID.	There is a need to obtain a clear understanding of what the PID identifies and how versioning is applied to all stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research Infrastructure Manager ● Instrument Owner ● PID Manager ● Data Curator ● Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreed instrument practices 	O ¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁴ Source definitions below the table

¹⁰⁵ UKRI-STFC

<p>I2: Develop guidance and policies for the assigning of PIDs for instruments within the organisation.</p>	<p>PIDINST provides high-level domain-agnostic approaches. Applying the PIDINST metadata schema requires implementing organisational decisions effectively and consistently. This encourages the sharing and establishment of best practices within domains.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research Infrastructure Manager ● Instrument Owner ● PID Manager ● Data Curator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID guidance ● PID (minting) policy 	<p>O</p>
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Table 9: Instrument Practices

Sources ('From where?'):

- A) LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue
- B) [ORCID](#) community
- C) INRIA/Software Heritage use case
- D) INRAE/DipSO (department for Open Science) use case
- E) [WorkflowHub](#) - a registry of computational FAIR workflows
- F) [Signposting](#)
- G) PIDs in complex data citation workshop
- H) "EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices" workshop. Material: van Lieshout, N., van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2023). EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices. Webinar, 21 November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245076> Recording: <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/eosc-compliant-pid-implementations-practical-guidelines-implementing-best>

- I) Joint FAIR-IMPACT / FAIRCORE4EOSC¹⁰⁶ - Kernel metadata recommendations. Nordling, J., Hugo, W., Bingert, S., L'Hours, H., Ramezani, P., van Horik, R., Matthiesen, M., Lager, L., Caminha Juaçaba Neto, R., & van Lieshout, N. (2025). Kernel Metadata - Agreed Recommendations on Metadata for Persistent Identifiers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15096004>
- J) Sensitive Data & Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Repository Lifecycle Factors. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12774337>
- K) Sensitive Data: Persistent Identifier (PID) Semantics Gaps. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12774041>
- L) CESSDA Training Team (2024). *CESSDA Data Archiving Guide* version 3.0. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC. <https://dag.cessda.eu/Chapter-4/5-Updates-and-versioning>
- M) Versioning - UK Data Service <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/format-your-data/versioning/>
- N) UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA use case
- O) UKRI-STFC
- P) INRIA/Software Heritage: [Software Heritage and IPOL, a fruitful collaboration towards reproducible research](#)

¹⁰⁶ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

5. Conclusions & next steps

This report outlines the guidelines for end users to use PIDs effectively in their research. It introduces PIDs, explains their benefits, and outlines some of the available PID types. The main body of the report details the scope of work for seven use case partners and describes the research context in which the PID recommendations apply. Key concepts are clarified, and specific themes group the recommendations.

A dedicated appendix offers additional reading for a broader understanding of how this work fits within the larger EOSC framework. Throughout this project’s lifespan, the task members have engaged with various research communities and PID experts to shape the recommendations outlined in this report. The details of these interactions are documented in an annex, alongside key insights that help contextualise the development of the final recommendations on PID use for end users.

The next step is to communicate our findings extensively and to increase their visibility as well as usability, e.g., by publishing the recommendations as a stand-alone resource on the project website and incorporating them into the workflows of relevant forthcoming EOSC-funded projects. The guidelines developed through this work on PIDs will become part of the Key Output (KO) titled “User-tailored guidelines for PIDs (policy and practice)”. These recommendations will also be included in the FAIRCORE4EOSC¹⁰⁷ project’s Knowledge Base¹⁰⁸, as part of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit¹⁰⁹ (CAT).

¹⁰⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

¹⁰⁸ Not yet published. Expected to be published during spring 2025.

¹⁰⁹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

APPENDIX A: Use case topics & structure and related definitions

Key definitions of the cross-cutting themes

Terminology related to key concepts in FAIR data management can vary significantly, which may cause confusion or hinder effective collaboration among stakeholders. Therefore, it is essential to clearly define the contexts and meanings of these terms to ensure a shared understanding of their underlying meaning and implications on the research lifecycle. In this section, we describe the key definitions of the cross-cutting themes for all use cases jointly to explore. The cross-cutting themes are illustrated in [Appendix A](#).

Granularity, in general, can be defined as “the scale or level of detail in a set of data”¹¹⁰ or “the ability to represent and operate on different levels of detail in data and information”.¹¹¹ The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Data Granularity Working Group (WG) used a use-case approach to explore best practice implementations of data granularity across infrastructures and services. The WG distinguished the following recommendations, with the support of previous RDA efforts:

- Entity Characteristics: Entities should have a core set of defining characteristics and relationship properties.

¹¹⁰ Stevenson, A. (2010). Oxford Dictionary of English. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780199571123.001.0001>

¹¹¹ Keet, C. M. (2010). A Top-Level Categorization of Types of Granularity. In J. Yao (Ed.), Novel Developments in Granular Computing: Applications for Advanced Human Reasoning and Soft Computation (pp. 92–130). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-60566-324-1.ch005>

- Metadata: Infrastructure should leverage metadata to enable and support detailed documentation of data granularity.
- Data Policy: Policies must be established to ensure and promote the management of data granularity.
- Discovery & Access: Infrastructure providers should implement methods to improve discovery and access across various levels of data granularity.
- Identification & Citation: Infrastructure should establish mechanisms for identifying, citing, and tracking entities at different granularities.
- Examination: Stakeholders should regularly review and assess how to best support data granularity within their context.
- Terminology: Stakeholders should adopt the terminology outlined in this document to promote shared understanding and ensure interoperability concerning granularity.¹¹²

Scientific reproducibility, or ‘reproducibility’, which is closely linked to replicability and repeatability, is a fundamental principle of the scientific method. For a study's findings to be reproducible, the results from an experiment, observational study, or statistical analysis should be consistently achievable with high reliability when repeated.

Machine actionability describes information organized in a consistent format, allowing computers or machines to be programmed to interact with it effectively.

Versioning systematically tracks changes made to data, software, files, etc., over time. It involves creating and managing different product releases, each maintaining the same core function but offering improvements, upgrades, or customisations.

¹¹² Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2024). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

APPENDIX B: Setting the scene within EOSC

This section briefly describes the underlying EOSC landscape to which the FAIR-IMPACT project and this report relate, outlining the specific sections on PIDs.

What is EOSC

“EOSC is the European web of FAIR data and related services for research. Research data that is easy to find, access, interoperate, and reuse (FAIR).”

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) envisions a transformative approach to research outputs, promoting trusted and sustainable practices across scientific disciplines. By unlocking the full potential of research data, EOSC aims to accelerate discoveries and foster innovation, establishing Open Science as the 'new normal' while rewarding and teaching essential skills. This initiative seeks to define standards and develop tools and services that empower researchers to find, access, reuse, and combine results seamlessly. Central to this vision is creating a ‘Web of FAIR Data and Services’ in Europe, facilitated by the EOSC Federation—a trusted virtual network of existing infrastructures designed to store, share, and reuse FAIR research outputs across borders and disciplines. The EOSC aims to federate diverse data, research, and e-infrastructure nodes, creating a distributed system that enhances accessibility for European researchers. By augmenting this Federation with new services and tools, EOSC will provide coordinated entry points for researchers to navigate the entire research cycle—from discovery and data mining to storage, management, analysis, publication, and reuse—ultimately fostering a collaborative and interoperable research environment rooted in the FAIR principles.¹¹³ The ongoing build-up phase is the first phase of development of an operational EOSC Federation, which, at the time of writing this report, has launched its first Node: the EOSC EU Node.¹¹⁴

Guiding EOSC principles and papers

The guiding documents of EOSC covering topics related to PIDs are the “Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 1.2¹¹⁵”, which includes the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) in

¹¹³ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/EOSC-A_GA6_EOSC-slide-deck-May-2023.pdf

¹¹⁴ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/about/eosc-eu-node>

¹¹⁵ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

section eight, “A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹¹⁶”, and “PID Architecture for the EOSC¹¹⁷”.

Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 1.2

This Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) defines the general framework for future strategic research, development, and innovation activities about the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This framework will be developed and further defined in the context of the EOSC Partnership proposed under the Horizon Europe Programme. The SRIA defines the driving forces in building EOSC and developing the EOSC Ecosystem, including main objectives, key principles, and related recommendations for achieving a well-functioning EOSC. Furthermore, the SRIA identifies PIDs as one of the crucial components needed to achieve that goal. The other key components are metadata and ontologies, FAIR metrics and certification, authentication and authorisation infrastructure, user environments, resource provider environments, and the EOSC interoperability framework.

The SRIA outlines that PIDs must be issued rapidly and at scale during data generation and support tracking throughout the research lifecycle, including versioning and provenance. Key areas for development include creating trusted PID infrastructures for emerging resources (e.g., instruments, software), enhancing machine-actionable PID tools, and integrating PIDs into FAIR data management workflows. Furthermore, fine-grained access control for PIDs and improved technical interoperability in EOSC are needed, alongside developing a PID policy that accommodates various maturity levels and emerging PID types.

The work of T3.2 responds to several of the recommendations of SRIA, e.g., using different types of PIDs for different research objects gives more reliable and semantically meaningful means to provide rich metadata to support research and appropriately attribute and track the use of valuable research objects. There are emerging technologies, standards, and organisations to support many of these. However, data uptake has been limited due to a lack of commonly accepted approaches and clear business cases for their use. Software tools must address data objects reliably, and PIDs provide a means to do this. In these applications, PIDs need to be issued and accessed rapidly and at scale at the data generation stage and to be accessed across the research lifecycle. PIDs, thus, need to be assigned at an appropriate granularity for the application to support addressing data objects within a more extensive aggregation. Versioning and tracking through the data lifecycle would also need to be

¹¹⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

¹¹⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schwardmann, U., Fenner, M., Hellström, M. et al., PID architecture for the EOSC – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture PID Task Force (TF), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/525581>

supported to accurately record the provenance of data from raw through fully quality-assured data to actual results.

Key areas for development include creating trusted PID infrastructures for emerging resources (e.g., instruments, software), enhancing machine-actionable PID tools, and integrating PIDs into FAIR data management workflows. Tools and standards supporting machine-actionable PIDs have been developed over recent years, including PID Kernel Information and PID Type Registries, but they are not yet mature or widespread. Furthermore, fine-grained access control for PIDs and improved technical interoperability in EOSC are needed, alongside updating the EOSC PID Policy to accommodate various maturity levels and emerging PID types.

A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The EOSC PID Policy¹¹⁸ (hereby referred to as ‘the Policy’) was authored by the EOSC FAIR WG and the EOSC Architecture WG in 2020. The Policy defines the PID infrastructure's roles and components and establishes expectations through definitions, guidelines, and usage requirements. It is written for senior decision-makers and service providers to achieve harmonisation of the EOSC infrastructure regarding PID implementation.

The Policy sets out 10 principles that guide PID implementation and usage. The principles outline, for example, that the EOSC PID Policy helps ensure a PID infrastructure is available for the long term by, e.g., accommodating an extensive range of use cases without putting any unnecessary barriers in place. PIDs are to be used as the preferred method for referencing objects. Furthermore, the Policy provides guidelines for ensuring adherence to the FAIR principles, especially interoperability, and for building a mature and sustainable infrastructure. Regularly updating the Policy ensures that it aligns with the most recent developments in the PID landscape.

As the Policy outlines, the PID Ecosystem refers to the collection of standards, services, actors, and roles required to ensure that PIDs are unique and remain resolvable over time. The PID roles outlined in the Policy are PID Authority, PID Service Provider, PID Manager, PID Owner, PID User, and PID Schema.

PID Architecture for the EOSC

The EOSC document PID Architecture (hereby referred to as ‘the Architecture’) for the EOSC¹¹⁹ defines which key components must be in place for an architecture for PIDs aligned

¹¹⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R., Manghi, P. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

¹¹⁹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schwardmann, U., Fenner, M., Hellström, M., Koers, H. et al., PID architecture for the EOSC – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working

with a set of key stakeholders. The architecture further delineates the interoperability opportunities involved in PID services within the framework of EOSC.

The Architecture provides guidelines for PID applications, e.g.:

- Kernel Information: the set of eligible kernel information types for a specific kind of digital object should be defined in so-called kernel information profiles
- Sustainability and persistence of PID systems: an identifier and its underlying infrastructure must capture robust metadata and provide it consistently and reliably. The expectation of persistence is based on cross-institutional arrangements vital in institutional failure, with an agreed set of rules abided by trusted PID Authorities and PID Service Providers.
- Sensitive data: PIDs are also used for sensitive data and have specific implications for implementing PIDs. For example, part of the metadata might be restricted, so fine-grained access control is needed for creating, updating, and accessing PID records.

However (see last bullet point above), **the FAIR-IMPACT project advises against including sensitive metadata in the kernel metadata**, as outlined in recommendation G1 (Kernel Metadata).

Group (WG) Architecture PID Task Force (TF), Publications Office, 2020,
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/525581>

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APPENDIX C: Community engagement

FAIR-IMPACT project WP3 has arranged several workshops to support research communities in establishing PIDs for different types of datasets, workflows, and research objects, gaining input on the PID best practice guidelines provided in this report.

Event name	Event format & date(s)	Purpose of event	Key takeaways	Target audience
PID best practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts, and related services ¹²⁰	Online May 25, 2023	To define best PID practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts, and related services. Topics covered: complex citations in practice, precise Identification of arbitrary subsets of (dynamic) data and FDOs for citation of digital artefacts.	When referring to a “collection,” which is also a digital object (DO), a good practice is to assign all included DOs with metadata, including license information. Workflow automation and tools (for) integration can make it easier for researchers to cite, but metadata quality checks may be complex with automated PID minting processes.	Invited: FDO Initiative, RDA Complex Citations WG or RDA Data Citations WG, RDA Data Citation WG, AGU Data Citation Community practices + open to everyone, e.g., data stewards
Harmonised PID practices for protected data ¹²¹	Onsite EOSC Symposium 2023, Madrid	To create a mutual understanding of PID practices for protected data, use cases such as Identifiers.org and its protected data feature and Sensitive Data Handling in the	In addition to the FAIR principles or general reasons to use PIDs, many open answers were related to changes: an existing data set is	EOSC community, data stewards, research data managers, PID managers

¹²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/pid-best-practices-complex-data-citation-semantic-artefacts-and-related>

¹²¹ <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/unconference-session-harmonised-pid-practices-for-protected-data/>

	September 21, 2023	Social Sciences should be examined. Participants reflected on the factors that trigger the generation of a new PID.	digitalised, there is a new version of the dataset, data is deposited, or there are changes in object/data, metadata, or rights. Correction of errors was seen as the most valid reason for minting a new PID. Kernel metadata is a complex topic, as the function it needs to serve splits people. Kernel metadata can help assure provenance, provide technical and descriptive metadata, and inform about sensitivity levels and access rights.	
EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices: Exploring PIDs in different research workflows ¹²²	Online November 21, 2023	To demonstrate concrete tools, policies, and developments within the realm of PIDs from the EOSC projects and use that to fuel further innovation through the FAIR IMPACT Open Support Call in January 2024. The workshop included an introduction to PIDs and their place within EOSC, a presentation on how PIDs are relevant within the general research lifecycle and various actors' roles	If depositing datasets in multiple repositories, make use of related identifiers in the DOI metadata. ¹²³ The owners' perspective and selection of appropriate PID services are also substantial and not covered by the EOSC PID Policy. Data workflows and PID maintenance are complex.	Data stewards, research data managers, PID managers, metadata/PID enthusiasts, PID policymakers

¹²² van Lieshout, N., van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2023). EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices. Webinar, 21 November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245076>

¹²³ https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

		and responsibilities within that lifecycle, and an introduction to the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT), which multiple actors can use within the research lifecycle to assess their compliance with the EOSC PID policy. Lastly, participants were split into three breakout sessions on PID usage within publications, software, or datasets to discuss current issues and possible solutions with a topic expert.		
Synchronisation Force series: PID workshops ¹²⁴ Workshop titles: Defining the roles of the EOSC PID Policy (2022), Trust and Sustainability (2023), and Collaboration Opportunities on PIDs (2024).	Online November 22, 2022 November 30, 2023 October 1, 2024	To foster ongoing dialogue and collaboration across various projects, initiatives, and stakeholders within the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems. They aim to minimise redundancy, promote widely adaptable solutions, and ensure sustainability. This collaborative approach aims to transfer outcomes to the relevant EOSC Partnership and current and future EOSC stakeholders. Throughout the project, the Synchronisation Force has hosted three online workshops (during the autumn of 2022, 2023 & 2024) that have brought together FAIR and EOSC ecosystem projects, infrastructures, and	Building sustainability and collaboration structures around PIDs in the context of the EOSC Federation and beyond is a multi-layer issue that requires the inclusion of several stakeholders. End-user involvement ensures PIDs' sustainability, persistence, and resolvability. Data stewards play a significant role in communicating the value and functionality of PIDs to the researchers. Integrate widely used and adopted PIDs into institutional workflows per	Key representatives from EOSC projects, infrastructures, representatives, and working groups.

¹²⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/synchronisation-force>

		initiatives across Europe. These workshops assess the progress on the FAIR-IMPACT focus areas and SRIA objectives.	interoperability capabilities. The issues and risks within the PID landscape call for more social intervention, with growing support and endorsement from the research community.	
Findability in FAIR: Touchpoints between EOSC and Open Web Search ¹²⁵	Onsite EOSC Symposium 2024, Berlin October 22, 2024	To explore novel ways for current and future collaboration in findability (F) in FAIR and how this collaboration contributes to future goals for FAIR data and principles in the context of EOSC. It is essential to address transparency in developing search applications and tools and widen the collaboration to benefit the research community. Synergies within science-search-focused contexts through examples from OpenWebSearch.eu, FAIRCORE4EOSC, and FAIR-IMPACT were explored, discussing how improved findability impacts science, industry, and society.	There is a demand for more concrete best practice examples of PID implementation and usage related to the various research lifecycle workflows, clearly also showcasing the benefits involved. Cross-stakeholder and cross-domain collaboration on findability generates comprehensive results and increased impact.	EOSC community research data management experts, PID/data managers

Table 10: Community engagement through events

¹²⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/news/event-highlight-fair-impact-unconference-session-findability-eosc-symposium-2024> <https://fair-impact.eu/events/other-fair-events/eosc-symposium-2024>